

USE OF MARKETING STRATEGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE BUSINESS ENTERPRISES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article aims to increase the number of functions and characteristics of goods in business enterprises, develop new models and variants of quality goods, update the characteristics of goods, and increase profits.*

Keywords: *enterprise, business, marketing strategy, product, market, profit.*

Introduction. The development of small business, which is the priority sector of the economy of our republic, is a factor in solving many tasks in the social and economic spheres of our country. The fact that a wide path has been opened to the development of small business and private entrepreneurship ensures the rapid development of the country's economy. The importance of small business and private entrepreneurship is increasing in the conditions of the modernization of our country. The share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the GDP of our country is increasing year by year. Today, as a result of their operation of many modern production, service and other service facilities, the standard of living of the population is improving, and our neighborhoods and villages are becoming prosperous. Therefore, in the following years, a number of innovations, opportunities and privileges are being created in order to further develop this field. The development of small business enterprises that participate in rapidly changing markets and have just entered the world of business directly depends on the efficiency of economic activity, and marketing activity has an important effect on it. According to marketing theory, the factors affecting the consumer are divided into controlled and uncontrollable groups. Marketers, using controlled factors, influence the minds of buyers and form the tendency of consumers to buy this particular product. Therefore, human needs are susceptible to external factors, especially the elements of the marketing complex. For example, in small and private enterprises that produce sewing products, it is possible to attract buyers faster by providing a model and additional decorations without changing the price and cost of the product. In this case, even if the price factor does not change, the demand will increase. In this case, the change in the product element of the marketing mix increases the interest of the customers in this product and the volume of the product sold in the market increases. Therefore, special attention should be paid to marketing research when planning product types in the production program. The function of marketing in the conditions of a market economy is to create opportunities for organizing free and competitive exchange activities in order to significantly coordinate the balance of supply and demand.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. An increase in the volume of product sales in the market represents the effectiveness of marketing. Marketing effectiveness is the result of the marketing activities of the manufacturer and seller, which is measured by indicators such as sales volume growth, profit, and market share. Therefore, as a result of marketing activities, it is possible to change the effect

on the total profit and sales volume. The ratio of the marketing effect to the funds spent to achieve it is the economic efficiency of marketing activities. Determining and studying the needs of consumers, adapting goods and services to cover their needs, engaging in their advertising, as well as supplying them in the required amount is the main task of marketing. Knowing the principles and basics of marketing activities helps to reduce the risk in business, the existing conditions,

The use of marketing in small business enterprises, especially the implementation of marketing strategies, is of great importance. The marketing strategy consists in aligning the company's capabilities with the market situation, defining complex means of achieving the set goals.

The task of the marketing strategy is aimed at regularly determining and retargeting the directions for the development, increase and profitability of all types of activities of the enterprise. Below are some of the main marketing strategies that businesses can choose from:

Market development strategy. Its purpose is to increase the volume of sales by introducing existing goods into new markets.

Product development strategies. It is aimed at increasing sales due to the development of new and improved goods for the markets where the enterprise operates. This strategy is manifested by increasing the number of functions and characteristics of the product and thereby expanding the market, developing new models and variants of goods of different quality levels, and updating the characteristics of the product.

As mentioned above, the firm's strategies are mainly focused on the objectives of increasing sales volume share and profit. Growth objectives can be expressed at 3 levels:

1. Growth relative to the main market.
2. Workb growth according to the output chain
3. Integration and integrated growth.
4. Growth through diversification based on opportunities outside the usual activity zone.

Market penetration strategy. It will try to increase the volume of sales in the existing markets. It can be achieved through various methods, namely: primary demand development; increase its market share; capture other markets; restore its position in the market through protection; improving the quality, that is, improving the performance of the product as a set of features; supplementing or expanding the range of existing goods using external means; rationalization of the range of goods, i.e. modification of the range of goods to reduce production and sales costs.

An integration strategy can be justified when the firm is able to increase its profitability by controlling the strategically important links in the production and sales chain. It is necessary to distinguish between "forward" and "backward" integrations and horizontal integration:

- Backward integration strategies are used to stabilize or protect a strategically important source of supply and learn new technology.
- Forward integration strategies are used to ensure control over sales channels.
- The goal of the horizontal integration strategy is to find certain competitors and strengthen the company's position by controlling them.

The strategy of growth through diversification - the firm looks for new types of activities that complement the activities in the technological and commercial plan, going beyond the scope of the industrial chain in which it operates.

Competitive strategies - analyzing competitors to determine what competitive advantages the firm can use against its most dangerous competitors.

Thus, in the conditions of modernization of the economy, the application of marketing strategies in small businesses and entrepreneurial enterprises is aimed at ensuring their competitiveness by increasing their profitability.

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